
REGIONALISATION FROM BELOW: INFORMAL CROSS-BORDER TRADE BETWEEN BRAZZAVILLE AND KINSHASA

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Abstract

This chapter delves into the intricate relationship between the informal cross-border trade between Kinshasa and Brazzaville and the process of regionalisation in the Congo Basin. Using social network theory, Foucault's concept of power, and various theories on the African state, it is argued that the informal trade between these two cities has always been interconnected with regionalisation in the Congo Basin, both before and during colonisation, and continues to be so in the postcolonial era. Despite efforts by colonial and postcolonial states to restrict this trade, it has persistently eluded control. The networks of actors involved often extend to other parts of Africa and beyond, suggesting that this trade also fosters interregional integration in Africa and contributes to grassroots globalisation.

Through qualitative research with Congolese traders engaged in cross-border trade in Kinshasa, this chapter reveals how trade and regionalisation are interlinked in the Congo Basin. It presents evidence of the trade's resilience against attempts by both colonial and postcolonial states to suppress it. Ironically, these states have, at times, acknowledged the significance of cross-border trade and permitted its continuation under certain circumstances. Ultimately, it demonstrates how this trade supports, sustains, and expands regionalisation in the Congo Basin as well as interregional integration across Africa.

Keywords: informal cross-border trade, regionalization, the Congo Basin, interregional integration, grassroots globalization.

Résumé

Ce chapitre se penche sur la relation complexe entre le commerce transfrontalier informel entre Kinshasa et Brazzaville et le processus de régionalisation dans le bassin du Congo. À l'aide de la théorie des réseaux sociaux, du concept de pouvoir de Foucault et de diverses théories sur l'État africain, il est soutenu que le commerce informel entre ces deux villes a toujours été lié à la régionalisation dans le bassin du Congo, avant et pendant la colonisation, et continue de l'être à l'ère postcoloniale. Malgré les efforts déployés par les États coloniaux et postcoloniaux pour restreindre ce commerce, celui-ci a constamment échappé à tout contrôle. Les réseaux d'acteurs impliqués s'étendent souvent à d'autres régions d'Afrique et au-delà, ce qui suggère que ce commerce favorise également l'intégration interrégionale en Afrique et contribue à la mondialisation à la base.

À travers une recherche qualitative auprès de commerçants congolais engagés dans le commerce transfrontalier à Kinshasa, ce chapitre révèle comment le commerce et la régionalisation sont liés au Congo.

Mots clés : Le commerce informel transfrontalier, régionalisation, le bassin du Congo, intégration internationale, mondialisation de base. .

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INTRODUCTION

This article examines the interplay between informal cross-border trade (ICBT) between Kinshasa and Brazzaville and the process of regionalisation in the Congo Basin. Drawing from social network theory, Foucault's concept of power, and theories on the African state, the article posits that the relationship between informal cross-border trade and regionalisation has been significant both before and during colonisation and continues to be so in the postcolonial era. Despite state opposition to this trade since the colonial period, it has persistently circumvented both colonial and postcolonial authorities. Cross-border coalitions in the Congo Basin have bolstered the trade, with actor networks extending to other parts of Africa and beyond, contributing to interregional integration and grassroots globalisation.

Beyond this, this article provides evidence that informal cross-border trade predates colonisation and has withstood attempts by both colonial and postcolonial states to curtail it. It also reveals how political turmoil and wars have created opportunities for some actors to accumulate wealth through illicit trade, with state officials from both Brazzaville and Kinshasa complicit in these activities. Finally, it shows how cross-border trade contributes to globalisation as well as it maintains, supports, and expands regionalisation in the Congo Basin and interregional integration in Africa.

Previous studies have focused on various aspects of Congolese involvement in illicit trafficking of diamonds (De Boeck 2001), cannabis (Hunt 2016), migrants (Tshimpaka and Inaka 2020), and imported goods (Titeca 2009; Ayimpam 2013). Others have explored the historical evolution of the trade (MacGaffey 1983; Ayimpam 2010) or the broader factors shaping the trade and its impact on the DRC (De Herdt and Marysse 1999; De Boeck 2001). Studies have also examined the intersections of history, economics, politics, and sociocultural factors in shaping trade (Kongo 1986; Brülhart and Hoppe 2011; Ayimpam 2014).

Research has also focused on the actors involved in informal trade, including foreign traders, disabled people, small-to-medium-sized retailers, multinational informal traders, and local smugglers known as "les Romains" (MacGaffey and Bazenguissa-Ganga 1998; 2000; Dzaka-Kikouta 2002; Brülhart and Hoppe 2011; Ayimpam 2013; 2014). The impact of the trade on the country includes contributions to poverty reduction (Ayimpam 2010; 2014), job creation (Brülhart and Hoppe 2011), strengthening business, family, or friendship ties (MacGaffey and Bazenguissa-Ganga 1998; 2000), economic

integration of the two cities (Kongo 1986; Brülhart and Hoppe 2011), and grassroots globalisation (Ayimpam 2014).

Despite the richness of this literature, it contains contradictions and gaps regarding causal factors, the actors involved, and the impacts of this trade in the regionalization in the Congo basin region. This article addresses these concerns and provides new evidence for a more nuanced understanding of this trade.

The article is organised as follows: The first section covers the conceptual, theoretical, and methodological tools used in the study. The second section provides a historical analysis of informal cross-border trade in Africa, with a focus on the DRC. The last section discusses the findings, arguing for the interdependence of informal cross-border trade and regionalisation in the Congo Basin.

1. Conceptual, theoretical, and methodological framework

This section begins by defining key concepts of this study: informal cross-border trade and regionalization. It then provides a concise introduction into network theory, Foucault's notion of power, and theories on the African state as the theoretical tools employed in this study. It ends with a presentation of the study's research method.

1.1. Concepts of Informal cross-border trade and Regionalisation

1.1.1. Informal cross-border trade

The concept of informal cross-border trade (ICBT) is grandiloquent; there is thus need to use it wisely (Ayimpam 2010). The ICBT can be understood as the unrecorded exchange of goods and services across national borders conducted by traders out outside of an official framework (Ackello-Ogutu and Echessah 1998. This trade can involve goods that are legitimately produced but that escape the government regulatory framework (Titeca and de Herdt 2010). The aim of the trade is to avoid certain tax and regulatory burdens such as the payment of duties and charges. To do so, traders resort to under-invoicing (i.e., declaring a lower quantity, weight, or value of goods in order to pay lower import duties), misclassification (i.e., falsifying the description of goods so that they are misclassified as goods subject to lower duties), or large-scale bribery (Ama *et al.* 2013).

A common factor in these definitions is the act of the unrecorded movement of goods and/or services across an international border. Yet it seems more difficult to determine a clear differentiation between informal movements across borders and illegal or criminal movements: the two seem to overlap and the difference between them seems fluid, if not ambiguous. For that reason, an

important literature on cross-border trade in African has questioned this dualism or binaries between informal–formal, official–unofficial and legal–illegal (Roitman 2005; Titeca and de Herdt 2010; Titeca and Flynn 2014). By denying the existence of these conceptual boundaries, this literature suggests that cross-border research focuses more on how informality and formality are related to each other.

Hence, Meagher (2003) defines informal cross-border trade as the importation and exportation of legal goods outside of official channels, and distinguish it from the criminal form which involves the movement of illegal goods. The former rarely threatens state legitimacy, whereas the latter undermines it because it involves legally prohibited goods (Kuhane 2017).

This differentiation is useful in the context of cross-border trade between Kinshasa and Brazzaville where illegal cross-border traders are regarded as those who trade with illegal goods without using official border posts – locally called *traffiquants* (illegal dealers, traffickers). They are also pejoratively referred to as *batu ya mongemba* for their practice of crossing the powerful Congo River on canoes or pirogues. Informal cross-border traders, by contrast, carry legal goods, use modern ships, ferries, or canoes, and pass-through Kinshasa's official border post at Beach Ngobila, though they avoid the customs services or pay lower customs duties. This study focuses on the latter, the informal cross-border trade.

1.1.2. Regionalization

According to many scholars, regionalization can be regarded as a growing process of economic, cultural, scientific, diplomatic, political, and military integrations within a given region (Hettne, Van Langenhove and Farrell 2016). As a political and/or economic process, it can best be perceived as a process of setting up political, economic, cultural and geostrategic regions by a particular group of states for the purpose of their integration (Kacowicz 1999; Hoshiro 2019). The process of regionalization by the governments of two or more states to establish voluntary associations and to pool together resources to create common functional and institutional arrangements is called regionalism. According to Hurrell (1995), Kacowicz (1999) and Hettne, Van Langenhove and Farrell (2016), regionalism can be understood as a political effort to establish an organisation of states in a geographically limited space. Since its main actors are governments; therefore, it can be seen as an artificial, top-down process, or a regionalization from above (Kacowicz 1999; Hoshiro 2019).

However, regionalization can also be spontaneously established by several non-state actors from different countries through their various interactions in each region. According to Hurrell (1995) and Hoshiro (2019), such regionalization can be understood as an increase in the cross-border flow of capital, goods, ideas, and people, in the development of complex social

networks and in the creation of a transnational integration of people within a specific geographical area. This socially driven regionalization process, which is not strictly controlled by governments, but is led by non-state actors (firms, Ong's, individuals), is commonly conceptualized as regionalization 'from below' (Mbembe and Rendall 2000), bottom-up regionalization (Kacowicz 1999; Hoshiro 2019). It is precisely this category of regionalization from below that interests us in this study.

1.2. Theoretical tools

This study employs three theoretical frameworks: social network theory, Foucault's concept of power, and theories concerning the African state. First, social network theory is particularly valuable for examining informal cross-border trade (ICBT) (Mutopo 2010). A social network consists of individuals who exchange information or commodities on a reciprocal and voluntary basis, a common practice among informal cross-border traders in the DRC. By analysing social networks, we can gain a deeper understanding of how trade between Kinshasa and Brazzaville functions and contributes to the regionalisation of the Congo Basin. However, social network theory has its limitations in identifying the power dynamics among actors within these networks, which is where Foucault's theory of power becomes relevant.

Foucault (1975) posits that power is not a property or commodity owned or exerted by institutions, individuals, or groups. Instead, it is omnipresent and multidirectional, operating both top-down and bottom-up across various sites and scales. Power relations are mobile, asymmetrical, unbalanced, and context-dependent, involving discourse (systems of ideas) that allow for resistance. Power is inseparable from resistance, as individuals continually seek ways to escape power structures, often through diffuse resistance and micro-revolts. Foucault dismisses the notion of national sovereignty, arguing that states are never free from external interference. His understanding of power as pervasive and multidirectional, along with the concept of resistance, provides a framework for examining the complex roles of ICBT in shaping regionalisation in the Congo Basin and resisting state power.

To comprehend regionalisation and the intricate geographical, historical, and cultural conditions of border countries, this study also draws on theories of the African state. Scholars have identified patrimonialism as a key characteristic, where the right to rule is ascribed to individual leaders rather than the administration (Thomson 2010). In such states, rulers often misappropriate state resources and distribute them to ensure loyalty, with real power exercised through personal relationships rather than political institutions or bureaucracies. The distinction between private and public spheres is blurred, the rule of law undermined, and reforms tailored to suit personal interests (Clapham 1985). Bratton and Van de Walle (1994) describe neo-patrimonial regimes as those ruled by chief executives who maintain authority through personal patronage rather than ideology or law. Bureaucrats

in these regimes seek to increase personal wealth and status rather than perform public service. Neo-patrimonial regimes rely on patron-client exchanges, where patrons provide public sector jobs or socio-economic favors to clients, who in turn mobilize support for the patrons.

Chabal and Daloz (1999) introduced the concept of the 'instrumentalization of disorder,' suggesting that African leaders exploit weak institutions to meet their needs. Bayart (2006) describes this as the 'politics of the belly,' where leaders resort to corruption instead of fulfilling their official duties.

Scholars have also differentiated between weak, failing, failed, and collapsed states in Africa (Rotberg 2004; Giorgetti 2010; Rotberg 2010). Rotberg (2004) uses the state's capacity to provide 'political goods'—such as human security, rule of law, political freedom, civil and human rights, healthcare, education, and infrastructure—as criteria for this differentiation. Roitman (2005) challenges the notion of weak or failing states, arguing that states reconstitute authority through networks of state and non-state actors and a mix of formal and informal practices. She introduces the concept of the "pluralization of regulatory authority," where the proliferation of regulatory forms in cross-border trade transforms representations of state power without diminishing it.

These theoretical approaches are insightful for explaining the persistence of ICBT between Kinshasa and Brazzaville despite state efforts to curtail it, the porosity of borders, and the role of informal traders in sustaining regionalisation from below in the Congo Basin.

1.3. Methods

This study was conducted in Kinshasa, the capital and principal city of the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC). Situated on the southern bank of the Congo River, it faces Brazzaville, the capital of the neighbouring Republic of Congo, located on the river's northern bank. These two cities are famously the closest capitals in the world, a key factor that fuels the intense activity between them. As the seat of government, parliament, and various public institutions, Kinshasa hosts the headquarters of all public trade and immigration agencies. It is also the primary base for most informal cross-border traders operating between Kinshasa and Brazzaville, making it a crucial site for this study.

The research employed qualitative methods, including unstructured interviews, in situ observation, and detailed life histories, across two distinct case studies. The first case study focused on the informal import of goods across the Lufu border (located along the DRC's southwest border with Angola). During fieldwork periods from 2016 to 2019, I followed Congolese traders who sourced affordable, authentic goods from Angola, Brazil, Namibia,

and South Africa to sell at lower prices in Kinshasa. A notable observation was the re-exporting of these goods from Kinshasa to Brazzaville.

The second case study, conducted in Kinshasa in 2021, involved in-depth interviews and extensive informal conversations to delve into the key actors involved in this informal trade. The research included interactions with five junior immigration officers, nine disabled persons, four informal customs brokers, six *Romains* (local smugglers), and fourteen self-employed Congolese traders.

This study was conducted in Kinshasa, the capital and principal city in the DRC. Previously named Leopoldville, Kinshasa has played an influential role in Congolese politics since colonisation. It is located on the southern bank of the Congo River, directly facing Brazzaville the capital of the neighbouring Republic of Congo. on the river's northern bank, The two cities are famous for being the closest two capitals in the world, an important reason for the hive of activity between them. As seat of government, parliament, and the public institutions, Kinshasa is where all public trade and immigration institutions are headquartered. It is also where most informal cross-border traders between Kinshasa and Brazzaville operate, making it an instructive location for this study.

The study used qualitative research methods, including unstructured interviews, observation *in situ*, and in-depth life histories, in two different case studies. In the first I collected data on the informal import of goods across the border of Lufu (located along the DRC's south-west border to Angola). During two fieldwork stints in 2016–2017 and 2018–2019, I followed Congolese traders who buy cheap, genuine goods from Angola, Brazil, Namibia, and South Africa to sell at lower prices in Kinshasa. A key observation here was traders re-exporting goods they had imported via Lufu to Brazzaville via Kinshasa.

In the second case study, conducted in Kinshasa from February to April 2021, I used in-depth interviews and extensive informal conversations to investigate more deeply the key actors that are involved in this informal trade. The research included five junior immigration officers, nine disabled persons, four informal customs brokers, six *Romains*, and fourteen self-employed Congolese traders. While deeper ethnographic work would have provided much richer data, this was not possible at the time as Congo-Brazzaville had closed its borders with the DRC due to presidential election. This resulted in the suspension of all trading activities at Ngobila Beach. Unexpectedly the border closure meant that interviews were held in respondents' homes, which allowed for longer and deeper discussions. It also allowed me to observe the interviewees' living conditions, a fact that certainly illuminates what they told me. The closure also meant that the *Romains* at Ngobila Beach were not working, and they agreed to a group interview.

The primary data was supported by official documents and newspaper reports, and scholarly publications on borders, regionalisation, and informal cross-border trade. Some of this information also allowed me to validate information from the primary sources.

2. A diachronic overview of ICBT between Kinshasa and Brazzaville

The history of cross-border trade between Kinshasa and Brazzaville is in the literature on cross-border trade in Africa. Hence, this section starts by providing an account of the resistance by informal cross-border traders across Africa to colonial authorities, African postcolonial states, and international events that have sought to curtail and eliminate their socio-economic activities. It then focuses on the history of this trade between Brazzaville and Kinshasa before, during, and after colonisation. It also highlights in which circumstances state authorities ignored this trade.

2.1. ICBT in Africa

Trade between ethnic communities and polities was a long-established socio-economic activity before colonisation (Gumbo 2012; Titeca and Flynn 2014). However, cartographical changes to the borders of these communities imposed by colonisation divided communities and the colonial imposition of taxation on trading activities drove many of these into informality. Although this trade thus came to be considered as illegal, state authorities have largely been unable to curtail it (Titeca 2009). It persists because of four main reasons.

The first reason was African traders not agreeing with abandoning an economic activity that had sustained their livelihoods long before the arrival of colonisation (Titeca 2009; Gumbo 2012; Titeca 2012). They tried to maintain their pre-colonial sociocultural and economic ties through cross-border contacts (Ndlela 2006). In many African countries informal cross-border trade even became a popular act of resistance against state control. Over the years it evolved in response to restrictive economic, trade, and migratory policies imposed by states (Lesser and Moisé-Leeman 2009). Many scholars of informal cross-border trade thus consider it as a source of economic freedom and empowerment for African people from below (MacGaffey 1983; Titeca 2012).

The second reason is related to African political systems and their poor economic management, and the public governance of postcolonial African states (Ndlela 2006; Kuhane 2017). From the 1970s, the latter came to be marked by patrimonialism, neopatrimonialism, tyranny, and a plethora of socio-economic problems (Bratton and Van de Walle 1994) whereby civilian or military dictators took over power (Britwum 2012) and nationalised and then mismanaged foreign owned enterprises. This resulted in economic degradation

of their countries (Souaré 2014). As a result, informal cross-border trade was transformed into a dominant survival strategy (Meagher 2003).

The third reason is a set of international events that had significant repercussions for African countries. These included the oil crisis of 1973 (Balassa 1985) and the strengthening of neoliberalism and concurrent implementation of structural adjustment programmes in the 1980s (Meagher 2003), with corollaries such as the proliferation of the privatisation of public enterprises and the rise of subcontracting or outsourcing. The end of the Cold War was correlated with an escalation of civil war in several African countries (Kalyvas 2001; Kalyvas and Balcells 2010). The advent of globalisation has been particularly consequential for informal cross-border trade, encouraging its expansion around the world (Meagher 2003). These global events had profound socio-economic consequences for African populations: impoverishment of communities, starvation or poor nutrition, proliferation of unemployment, wide-scale unfair dismissals of employees, and extreme proletarianization. In this situation informal cross-border trade was one of the few feasible alternative means of survival (Samaila 2011).

The last reason is the porosity of African countries' borders which facilitated cross-border, regional integration (Moyo 2020). Though the cross-border trade is not a new phenomenon because it is partly an extension of the previous, pre-colonial trade, the porosity of African countries' borders started with the creation of those African borders during colonisation. For that reason, colonial and post-colonial states regarded this trade as an illegal practice.

Despite efforts by colonial and postcolonial authorities to restrict informal cross-border trade, its continuity is evidence of the role that porous borders played in facilitating trade (Nshimbi, Moyo and Laine 2020). Border porosity can also be understood by the fact that, despite signed agreements between African governments to ensure the free movement of people, services, and goods between their countries, most states still require visas for entering their territories (Nkada 2011). Paradoxically, these same borders are highly porous and permeable because of a lack of control and monitoring due to poor or no management. Combating informal cross-border trade thus remains a challenge.

2.2. ICBT between Kinshasa and Brazzaville

Although cross-border trade between Kinshasa and Brazzaville is quite dissimilar from ICBT in Africa in general, there are however, some specific issues that resonate. In order to chronologically and critically review the literature on this trade, I will go back in time by analysing this trade from the pre-colonial through the colonial and post-colonial periods.

During the pre-colonial period specifically around the sixteenth century, people of the Tio kingdom traded between Kinshasa and Brazzaville and other areas in the central African region. The Tio were the main purveyors

of slaves but also traded in a wide variety of goods that the neighbouring Bakongo people pejoratively called them *Batéké*, “traders of all kinds”. In the early nineteenth century, the Bobangi people, involved in long distance trade between the Congo and Ubangi rivers, joined the *Batéké* to trade between Brazzaville and Kinshasa (Vansina 2018).

With the advent of the colonial labour market (1885-1960), the Belgian colonial authorities sought to eradicate this cross-border trading by criminalising it. Here it should be remembered that the colonisation of the Congo was initially the personal business (from 1885 until 1908) of a single individual, the Belgian King Leopold II. He set up and regulated a ferocious forced labour regime marked by the use of extreme violence (Hochschild 1998). Given the severity of Leopold II’s policies, many Congolese were not only coerced into forced labour but also lost their livelihoods (Nzongola-Ntalaja 2002). In the early twentieth century Leopold II’s forced labour regime was replaced by a dual labour market regime that was to last until decolonisation in 1960. It was characterised by unequal and racialised labour division between privileged white colonials and the underprivileged Congolese. Colonialists used the Poll Tax, which compelled Congolese people to work for cash incomes in European-dominated sectors of the economy, in order to ensure the availability of Congolese cheap workforce for the colonial administration and capitalist investors (Houben and Seibert 2013).

However, several riparian people continued trading between the two banks of the Congo River, to such an extent that their activities were seen as a dilemma by the colonial authorities (Ayimpam 2010). On the one hand, there was a concerted effort to stop this trade as it evaded taxation and led to a loss of national income. On the other hand, the colonial state was aware of the crucial importance of this trade for supplying the inhabitants of Leopoldville with goods and incomes. Consequently, it turned a blind eye to the trade during the Great Depression (the world economic crisis of 1929–1934) that affected the Belgian Congo to such an extent that unemployment occurred for the first time in Leopoldville.

After the DRC’s independence in June 1960, the ICBT grew despite efforts by the state to eradicate, control, or formalise it. The early 1960s saw an unprecedented rise in cross-border trade in line with a row of political crisis in the DRC (Ishako 2018). Kuhane (2017) in fact argues that ICBT in the DRC originated during this period principally due to economic mismanagement and the dissolution of the state and its administrative capacities. The trade then escalated during the Mobutu regime (1965–1997) (Titeca 2009; De Coster 2012). This tyrannical, kleptocratic, and patrimonial rule tore through the Congolese economic fabric in particular with its Zaireanization policy of 1973 that saw the expropriation of foreign-owned companies, forcing many people to adopt the *debrouillez-vous pour vivre* (fend for yourself) strategy (Kuhane 2017). In this situation, the informal economy became the means to survive for many economically disenfranchised Congolese (Devlieger 2018). MacGaffey

(1983) has shown that the trade enabled people from the middle and working classes to avoid proletarianization in the early 1980s, whereas people from the dominant class still managed to use it to accumulate wealth. In the mid-1980s Prime Minister Kongo Wa Dongo's government implemented a Structural Adjustment Programme, following recommendations from the International Monetary Fund. This resulted in the regress of the formal economy (De Herdt and Marysse 1999) and a significant growth of informal cross-border trade between Kinshasa and Brazzaville (Ayimpam 2013; Devlieger 2018).

Since the fall of President Mobutu in the then Zaïre and President Pascal Lissouba in Congo Brazzaville, in May and October 1997 respectively, both countries have experienced tense diplomatic relations. These have resulted in several cases of border closures, several brutal expulsions of undocumented *Kinois* (residents of Kinshasa) from the Republic of Congo back to the DRC, and bans by the DRC on imports of certain products from Brazzaville (Devlieger 2018). These policies have contributed to increasing illicit trafficking of people and goods across this border (Ayimpam 2013).

In sum, the account of ICBT between Kinshasa and Brazzaville contrasts and supports arguments proffered in the literature analysed above on ICBT in Africa. In terms of contrast, the fact that the Belgian Congo colonial state recognised the importance of informal cross-border trade to the extent that they refrained from preventing it under certain unprecedented circumstances brings a nuanced view to the literature on ICBT in Africa. The latter focused only on showing both the colonial and postcolonial states' restrictions against ICBT and trader resistance to that. The literature also did not pay any particular attention to the historical evolution of the key actors involved in the trade. The theoretical and empirical literature on informal cross-border trade in Africa thus applies only partially to the context of such trade between Kinshasa and Brazzaville. The literature does, however, explain the continuation of ICBT between Kinshasa and Brazzaville despite repeated waves of repression against it. The literature proposes that its continuity is explained by the resistance of the people to state control, the effects of international phenomena on the country, and the porosity of borders – all factors that apply to the DRC.

3. The ICBT and regionalisation in the Congo Basin

This section demonstrates how trans-border economic activities by three key Congolese actors contribute to interactions between informal cross-border trade and regionalisation in the Congo Basin. The actors are disabled people, immigration officials, and unofficial customs brokers.

3.1. Disabled cross-border traders in the Congo Basin

Disabled people (especially those who use tricycles, large three-wheeled motorcycles, as means of mobility) officially only have to pay 30% of

the fees when crossing the Congo River by ferryboat (De Coster 2012). According to Jean-Pierre Kibinda, the president of *l'Union des personnes handicapées pour les actions de développement* (UPHAD, the Union of Disabled People for Actions of Development), 600–700 disabled people cross the Congo River daily (Zengba and Nzela 2012). Often, however, they manage not to pay any fees by threatening customs officials. Consequently, they are sought after by trans-border traders and clandestine migrants who use them to avoid paying for custom duties or migration fees, respectively.

This study found that the disabled dominate the informal cross-border trade between Kinshasa and Brazzaville through three paid trans-border economic activities: they pretend to own the goods they carry, they broker for Congolese traders, and they smuggle goods. I examine each in turn.

Pretending to own expatriate traders' goods

Findings suggest that disabled people informally collaborate with expatriate traders, particularly West Africans and Lebanese. They help these traders import goods from Brazzaville to Kinshasa at reduced customs fees. From my respondents, I learned that West African traders often import clothes (especially rich bazins, boubous, sandals), beads, kitchen utensils, skin-lightening cosmetics, and pharmacopoeia products. According to them, these goods come from Senegal, Nigeria, Mali, Togo, Guinea Conakry, and Beni.

Likewise, the Lebanese also import many types of goods such as clothes, furniture, office supplies, and car parts. According to respondents, these Lebanese import their goods from China, Turkey, Lebanon, Morocco, Dubai, and Europe. Before arriving in Kinshasa, their goods transit to Brazzaville via the port of Pointe Noire. In doing so, they ease not only the movement of goods within the Congo Basin but also strengthen the socio-economic and cultural ties with the people from Niger or the Senegal Basin, as well as others from the rest of the world.

According to the disabled respondents, they use the privilege of being liable for only 30% of customs, transportation, and storage fees because of their disabilities to broker deals with West African or Lebanese traders. In these deals, these expatriate traders require the Congolese disabled people to transport their goods from Brazzaville to Kinshasa. These traders pay for the transport costs, even though these disabled persons hardly ever pay transportation fees. The traders also pay their disabled business partners a runner fee equivalent to 50% or 60% of the customs fees. When entering the DRC at the customs services in Kinshasa, the disabled person will pretend to be the owner of the imported goods from Brazzaville and pay the 30% customs fees in line with official regulations.

One of the disabled traders, Moto, described some of the background to such transactions between the disabled and expatriate traders:

As I am a Muslim, I was in the mosque one day when a Senegalese approached me to offer me my first deal. He was honest in telling me that he was able to pay all the customs fees. However, he just wanted to help me earn something more substantial because we pay 30% of the customs fees.

Building up relations of trust between disabled people and expatriate traders reinforces their ties. Disabled persons and expatriate traders have developed informal regulations or “moral codes” to grow these relations of trust in support of a functional business. The need for these systems of trust and collaboration that involve substantial amounts of money and significant value in goods it demonstrated in several cases of breach of trust and swindling that occurred in the early 1980s, as narrated by Bondeko:

Some of our friends used to vanish with money and goods belonging to West African traders. It was very nasty, such acts of theft.

Bomoyi added:

We are nobody, but only poor disabled people. But our brothers [Congolese disabled people] used to steal from expatriate traders who allowed us to earn money. Was it necessary to be so ungrateful to our benefactors?

To mitigate such breaches, disabled people and their collaborators have adopted two effective strategies since the 1980s. First, they have created a professional group from which from which unknown disabled people¹ and those with unknown accommodation² are excluded from dealing with expatriate traders. Secondly, it is highly recommended for expatriate traders to always deal with groups of three or four disabled people and not just with one person.

It is important to recall that official regulations have facilitated the emergence of a particular cross-border trade in which disabled people work between Kinshasa and Brazzaville. Not only does this regulation strengthen economic integration between the two sides of the Congo River, but it has also given rise to an informal trade which has several regional and interregional implications. Informal trade maintains, strengthens, and extends regional interactions in the Congo Basin. The trade facilitates development of mutual trust between nationals from across the Congo Basin with those of the Niger and Senegal basins.

¹ These are disabled people who are newcomers in cross-border trade and are still unknown or not familiarised with those who have been doing this trade before them.

² This concerns disabled people whose home addresses are not known by their counterparts.

Acting as brokers for Congolese traders

Previous studies have shown that disabled people assist Congolese trading between Brazzaville and Kinshasa (Ayimpam 2010; De Coster 2012; Devlieger 2018). However, while these studies provide vital information on informal business practices, relationships between disabled people and their clients, and their mutual expectations, they do not consider two related facts that this study raises as important to regionalisation. The first concerns the impact of the implementation of neoliberal restrictive trade policies against disabled people. The second relates to international solidarity between disabled people of Kinshasa and those in Brazzaville in response to these restrictive trade policies.

In 1988, the government of Prime Minister Léon Kengo wa Dondo severely restricted the customs exonerations granted to disabled people since the 1970s.

In line with Foucault's (1975) argument about human resistance to power and authority the disabled organised several public demonstrations against the restrictions placed on their rights. The government then demanded that they form an association whose members could then function as customs brokers. As a result of these steps, the disabled had to work with Congolese traders again and could no longer earn as much as they had before the implementation of the policy. One of the disabled, Mr Lokumu, explained:

Kengo wa Dondo, this man is awfully bad. He uprooted our job. He did not even have compassion for miserable and poor people like us. ... The customs brokers were a bluff. We only had this pride of wearing badges. But money, money, there was no money. We could not compete with other brokers who already had their clients.

Being unable to earn much in Kinshasa, the disabled people turned to international solidarity with their counterparts from Brazzaville. As in the DRC, disabled people in the Republic of Congo had to pay only a reduced rate on custom duties in their country. Finding that they were often conned by customs officials in Brazzaville when presenting themselves as owners of the goods being imported for Congolese traders from Kinshasa, they began to involve their counterparts from Brazzaville in their businesses. These counterparts would pretend to be owners of the imported goods from Kinshasa at the customs service in Brazzaville and would be charged the low fees; both sides would then share the dividends from their deals.

Overall, the implementation of neoliberal policies has negatively impacted cross-border trade. Discouraging disabled people from trading informally with expatriate traders has limited their contributions to regionalisation. However, they fought to maintain their trades by resisting power and adapting to these policies.

Smuggling imported goods

The third economic activity engaged in by disabled people is the smuggling of imported goods. This activity has been examined in previous studies that focused on describing how the smuggling went ahead (Ayimpam 2010; Devlieger 2018). This study provides more insight into the origin of the practice. Initially it had been collusion between state officials and disabled people, but the latter managed to exclude the former and to fully monopolise the smuggling.

Respondents acknowledged that they often refuse to pay customs fees even though the Congolese state has granted them an exemption from a large part of these fees. Being known as terribly angry people and using their physical disabilities as excuse or asset, they often engage in verbal arguments with customs officials and take advantage of their situations so that they manage to leave Beach Ngobila without paying any duties for their goods.

They learnt to do this from police and migration officials. According to them, they did not really need to smuggle goods because they were already making enough money by paying only 30% of the customs fees. But in the late 1980s police and immigration officials began to ask them for contributions of small bank notes in return for helping them to dodge the customs service altogether. They would tell them to pretend to be angry, create a little disturbance, play the victim, and then to leave. Since then, disabled people continue to use these methods, even without colluding with state officials.

What is worth highlighting here is how the involvement of disabled people in ICBT enables interregional informal trade networks to operate and strengthen their interrelationships in the Congo Basin, while interregional informal trade networks sustain the activities of the disabled people. Drawing on network theory, it could be noted that they engage in transnational networks that trade not only in the two Congo's, but also in much of the Congo Basin and other parts of Africa, as well as outside the continent. These ICBT produce and reproduce social networks that facilitate circulation of goods, persons, and economic and socio-cultural practices in the Congo basin. These circulations involve several relationships between the disabled Congolese with local and expatriate traders, state officials, and their counterparts from Brazzaville. Such webs of circulations reveal the extent to which commercial networks can challenge state regulations or use them for their own benefits. They also highlight the weakness of African states to control efficiently and effectively their borders. However, these social networks also actively participate in the "weakening" of the state through migratory and customs fraud. To paraphrase Roitman (2005), it could be noted that the role of the state and its regulation of borders appear paradoxical as state authorities simultaneously fight these illegal traders and facilitate them as well.

3.2 International involvement of officials in informal cross-border trade

The literature on informal cross-border trade has extensively explored the indirect involvement of state officials in the trade (De Coster 2012; Ayimpam 2014). Building on this literature, this study found that Congolese officials from both Brazzaville and Kinshasa openly participate in the reproduction, sustenance, and expansion of this trade. Although Congolese immigration officials from Kinshasa are officially supposed to control informal cross-border trading between Kinshasa and Brazzaville, they often enhance informal trade in collusion with their counterparts from Brazzaville. Officials from the DRC's Direction Générale de la Migration (DGM, the General Directorate of Migration) explained the reasons for their involvement in this trade and their interactions with their counterparts from Brazzaville. Their involvement secretly began in the early 1980s and evolved throughout the 1990s to become a widespread practice due to three main reasons.

First, the dire socio-economic situation experienced by Congolese state officials due to non-payment of salaries, widespread corruption in the public administration, and labour inequalities drove immigration officials to supplement their salaries with income from informal cross-border trade. One DGM official stated:

Our situation was horrible. We were very poorly paid. ... We use our professional positions and relations to trade with our friends from Brazzaville. We had to survive, feed our families. ... We had no choice.

Second, competition with others at the workplace and in the community resulted in many immigration officials turning to ICBT. Migration officials explained how they saw Congolese elites, their relatives, and cronies trading between Brazzaville and Kinshasa without paying any taxes or fees. They also observed how custom officials embezzled money by extorting traders or under-declaring the customs duties in the official documents and live off the gains like petit bourgeois. Seeing this, they decided also to venture into what seemed to be a lucrative business. As Butu Moyi explained:

Girlfriends, wives of the bosses of the Mobutu regime have made money here. They were not paying custom fees, taxes, transport. ... The same thing occurs after the collapse of Mobutu. ... Meanwhile, we are supposed to sit in our offices and get only crumbs. We were forced to look for money like them.

Mrs Loyenge added that

[c]ustom officials, even officers of lower ranks, make money every day. They bully traders and extract money from them. This is not enough; they do not declare all money that traders pay in the official documents. Look at how they live in luxury. They drive expensive cars

that they cannot afford with their salaries. ... We also decided to do the same thing in our own way.

Third, political crises, insecurity, and wars in the 1990s increased the involvement of officials in cross-border trade. Looting in Kinshasa in 1991 and 1993 destroyed the few companies that had remained and led to further job losses. In the Republic of the Congo, an armed conflict in 1993–1994 opposed militias under President Pascal Lissouba against those under Brazzaville Mayor Bernard Kolelas (Bazenguissa-Ganga 1999). In 1996–1997, Laurent Désiré Kabila, backed by Rwanda and Uganda, waged a war against Mobutu and pushed him from power in May 1997 (Turner 2013). In 1997, militias under politician Denis Sassou Nguesso, backed by Angola, ousted President Lissouba from power in Congo-Brazzaville (Bazenguissa-Ganga 1999). These crises offered opportunities for immigration officials on both sides of the Congo River to make quick fortunes. The officials interviewed in Kinshasa explained that their collaboration with officials from Brazzaville strengthened during this period. Butu Moyi explained it thus:

When Lissouba and Kolelas were fighting in Brazzaville, our friends [the Brazzaville officials] had to survive because their activities were paralysed as all trading activities were suspended. So, they sent us their goods or parcels through their trusted men or family members. ... The two lootings of Kinshasa in 1991 and 1993 affected us. We had nothing left. ... We increased deals with our friends from Brazzaville.

He went on to say:

Foreigners, several public authorities asked us to move their goods across to Brazzaville when Kabila's troops were approaching Kinshasa. ... It was a godsend for all those who had good contacts in Brazzaville to get money. ... Our friends [the officials in Brazzaville] were sending us several things to sell for them at the beginning of the war between Sassou and Lissouba.

The situation was thus one where state officials whose task it was to prevent illegal trade were themselves engaged in it. Here the scholarly debate on the notion of the dissolution of the Congolese state is of assistance. Opposed to Kuhane (2017), who postulated that Congolese state officials trade informally because of the non-existence of the state in the DRC, I draw on Chabal and Daloz (1999) notion of instrumentalization of disorder.

I thus argue that the Congolese state continued to exist but that some officials took advantage of the administrative disorder to engage in ICBT. I also bring in Olivier de Sardan's (2010) concept of practical norms, which refers to the real behaviour of state officials that differs from official norms and laws, to understand how state officials in Brazzaville and Kinshasa trade on the basis of their extra-official norms and regulations. Moreover, Bayard's notion

of politics of belly encapsulates in which ways this informal involvement of state officials in this trade typifies the inadequacy between state norms and their enforcement by the officials. Mbembe's (2000) concept of indirect private government also facilitates us to understand this trade as a response from unpaid or underpaid state officials to political elites. Consequently, a plethora of neo-patrimonial networks from the bottom sustains informal circulations of goods and people in in the Congo Basin.

Overall, the unofficial transnational collaboration between state officials in ICBT on both sides of the river is highly significant in relation to regional integration in the Congo Basin. Not only is this collaboration a strong indication of the porosity of the border between the two cities, but it also, in an unofficial manner, facilitates regional integration in the Congo Basin that the official governments of the two countries and international institutions have failed to implement. Here Mbembe's concept of indirect private government too is helpful for asserting that state authorities turn a blind eye to this trade, precisely because of the privatization of the state. This reality can also be better captured by Rotiman who argues that relationship between informal cross-border traders and the state is highly ambiguous as the state depends on these illegal economies for rents and redistribution

3.3 Informal customs brokers and *Romains*

Contrary to previous studies, findings of this study differentiate informal customs brokers from *Romains*. According to Ayimpam (2010) and Devlieger (2018), *Romains* are cross-border smugglers who are young people or young adults, generally living in working-class neighbourhoods near Kinshasa' city centre. They have been smuggling in *Beach Ngobila* since the 1970s, but their activities intensified when West African traders began to require their services from the 2000s. To smuggle their goods at Ngobila Beach, these *Romains* take any risk. If necessary, they would even throw themselves into the Congolese river loaded with a parcel weighing several dozen kilograms to escape customs. Literally, *Romains* (Romans) means inhabitants of Rome. According to Devliger, Rome is a nickname for Ngobila Beach because it is considered as a 'country within a country' where norms are set aside but anomie is accepted. Therefore, porters, smugglers of migrants or illegal goods, or hawkers are commonly referred to as *Romains*.

However, many informants asserted that the use of this term began in 1980, after the visit of the Roman Catholic Pope John Paul II to Kinshasa and Brazzaville. As this pope (called in Lingala "*Papa ya Roma*", i.e., the pope of Rome) had set foot on the beach of Brazzaville, the workers of this beach started to call this place "Rome" by analogy with the pope's place of residence. The term was also adopted at Ngobila beach.

Moreover, this study found differences between *Romains* and informal customs brokers operating at Ngobila Beach. *Romains* are only dockers

or porters working in Ngobila Beach. Because the *Romains* hang around Ngobila Beach, people can confuse them for informal customs brokers. This confusion is made easier because some informal customs brokers are former *Romains*. They have, however, changed their jobs and become intermediaries between traders and customs officials. The job of informal customs brokers is to negotiate reductions in customs fees with customs officials in favour of traders. The latter, in turn, pay them for this service. The brokers claim that their strong relationships with state officials in both Brazzaville and Kinshasa help them in their work. They have also built up a relationship founded on trust with expatriate or Congolese traders. Respondents stressed that West African traders need their brokerage services, and not the smuggling services of the *Romains*. The brokers also explained that they do not allow anyone to enter their professional niche easily because they deal with traders' monies and customs officers' commercial interests.

The empirical data of this study brought nuances to the literature on informal cross-border trade, border porosity, the meaning of borders, and regionalisation from below. In terms of meanings attributed to border posts and the creation of an informal professional niche among customs informal brokers from the two sides of the Congo River, one respondent explained that

'we consider Ngobila Beach to be a large forest full of game where anyone can find a place to hunt. But it is forbidden to hunt in our space'.

This parable simply means that everyone has the right to work and make a fortune at Ngobila Beach. This can be interpreted as a form of resistance, rejection, or ignorance of the authority of the state by believing that they cannot be prevented from working in the space of the border post that belongs to everybody. The parable also displays the existence of a quasi-inaccessible professional niche for these informal customs brokers who refuse to allow newcomers to enter their profession. According to some respondents, any newcomer must be sponsored by a practicing broker and these recruits must be accepted by the informal customs brokers in both Brazzaville and Kinshasa.

The last fact is the notion of border porosity. For many *Romains* and informal customs brokers, the Congo River is a road, creating a connection between two sides, not a border between them; to them Kinshasa and Brazzaville are the same city. To support their view, they referred to a song by Papa Wemba that recalls the strong linkages between these two cities.

Ebale ya Congo ezali lopango te, kasi ezali nde nzela.

The Congo River is not a fence or a barrier, but rather a road.

Inspired by this song, one of them contested the border by arguing that:

'The river is only a road as Papa Wemba said. ... I work; I do not steal. So, the border does not concern me. ... We do not care. ... Brazzaville and Kinshasa are one city for us'

Similarly, another one added:

'It is not God, the creator of this river, who declared that: "My Congolese people, this is a border between Kinshasa and Brazzaville"... Our politicians have just followed Europeans' ideas who declared the Congo River as a border. ... Only musicians like Papa Wemba understand that Brazzaville is equal to Kinshasa.'

Based on these perceptions, some of the traders believe that they have rights in both cities. Their perceptions are at odds with the official conception of nations, borders between them, and border posts guarding passage across. One can understand the traders' approach as a rebuttal from below of the Berlin conference's border creation. The traders' informal jobs allow them not only to sustain themselves financially but also to strengthen the region through the cooperation by the collaborators on both banks of the river.

In sum, one can argue that several structural and individual factors drive Congolese to informal cross-border trade between Kinshasa and Brazzaville. This informal job allows people from different social backgrounds and geographical areas to interact in the Congo Basin to the benefit of each other. Their transnational socio-economic and cultural networks, which consolidate relations of trust between Congolese and expatriates, are factors reinforcing the regionalisation of informal cross-border trade in the Congo Basin. This also applies to the establishment of informal regulation and the creation of an international professional niche which shows how regionalisation can emerge and be maintained and reinforced by exclusive groups of informal cross-border traders. Though the state has always sought to curb ICBT, the fact remains that it is through the interaction of these factors that socio-economic and cultural integration in the Congo Basin is maintained, strengthened, and invigorated.

CONCLUSION

The study demonstrates how regionalisation in the Congo Basin, and interregional integration more broadly, are facilitated and sustained by informal cross-border trade. This regionalisation, characterized by the cooperation of Congolese and foreigners in cross-border businesses, in turn, maintains and perpetuates informal cross-border trade. The reciprocal relationship between regionalisation and informal cross-border trade is supported by five key findings highlighted in this study.

First, the interdependent relationship between informal cross-border trade and regionalisation in the Congo Basin has existed since before colonisation and continues to this day. This study disproves theories that suggest informal cross-border trade is solely a colonial or postcolonial phenomenon.

Secondly, despite attempts by the colonial state to eradicate, control, and formalise it, informal cross-border trade has resisted all these measures. Colonial authorities even recognized its importance under certain unprecedented circumstances, demonstrating the trade's resilience and significance.

Thirdly, the postcolonial Congolese state also attempted to eliminate, monitor, or regulate informal cross-border trade. These efforts failed due to weak state institutions, which in turn allowed informal cross-border trade to flourish. The study highlights how the strength of informal networks often compensates for formal institutional weaknesses.

Fourthly, neoliberalism and the end of the Cold War had adverse effects on informal cross-border trade in the Congo Basin, restricting the regulatory space within which it operated. However, informal cross-border traders adapted to these new conditions and even managed to expand in terms of both the number of actors involved and the regional spaces they occupied.

Finally, throughout all the historical periods examined, the intersection of actors involved in informal cross-border trade, their commercial and social networks, their relationships of trust, and parallel trade regulations have cemented the relationship between informal cross-border trade and regionalisation. This study underscores the importance of these networks and relationships in sustaining both informal trade and regional integration.

Overall, the study provides a comprehensive understanding of the enduring and reciprocal nature of the relationship between regionalisation and informal cross-border trade in the Congo Basin, challenging previous assumptions and highlighting the adaptability and resilience of informal trade networks.

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